

ISic2759

I.Sicily inscription 2759

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

prayer

Material

terracotta

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2013.10.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

contrada Anguglia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175483

1. (X [.] (X X
2. (X) ἐν ὀνόματι τοῦ Κ (ὕριου) υ Ἰ(ησο) ὤ Χ(ριστοῦ)
3. ἄγιοι ἄγελο ²⁶ἄγγελοι²⁶ Ο ἐπιγ[ρ]άφ-
4. οντες υλιστίριον ²⁶ἰληστήριον = ἰλαστήριον?²⁶ ΤΟΤΟ
5. ΑΝΠΙ[.]ΕΛΟΣΕΡΓΟΝΙΤΑ
6. βοίθι μου ἰς ²⁶βοήθει μοι εἰς²⁶ τὸν καρπὸ [ν]
7. π (νεύματο) ς ΠΕΛΟΝΑΝ τὸ [ν] θ (εο) ὤ
8. (X X X X) θ (εὐ) ς
- 9.
10. (X) θ (εὐ) ς Κ (ὕριου) ς (X)
11. Γαυ (ρι) ἰλ Μιχ-
12. αἰλ.
13. (X)
- 14.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

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